

Workshop on Co-benefits + digital tools

Deliverable 1.1

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Antecedents (work before workshop): Based on previous ICRA’s work and experience (i.e. extensive literature review and part of the participatory process already carried out in the Girona Living Lab), ICRA has prepared all the necessary materials for the MULTISOURCE pilots to independently conduct their own workshops with stakeholders to select the co-benefits and indicators. A simulation workshop was carried out in June 2023 with the partners responsible by the pilots. In the 2023 annual meeting, a workshop took place to reduce the number of potential co-benefits and indicators. This report summarizes this workshop, which took place on June 5th, 2023, the first day of the 2023 MULTISOURCE annual meeting. The consortium partners selected the co-benefits and indicators “most likely to be selected” for monitoring the 7 MULTISOURCE pilots and developed factsheets to gather technical information on these indicators. In the end, 37 indicators and 40 factsheets were developed.

1.0 Welcome and goals

The session was organized in two working parts.

1.1 Part 1 - Group selection of environmental, socio-economic and disadvantages Indicators

The goal was to select together the indicators for monitoring *environmental*, *socio-economic* co-benefits and *disadvantages* based on their usefulness/relevance versus their complexity to be monitored (costs implicated, difficulties on collecting data etc).

1.2 Part 2 – Indicators Factsheet

The goal was to gather technical information, based on experts’ knowledge, about the indicators selected in the part 1 (i.e. data collection methods, frequency etc).

2.0 Part 1 - Group selection of environmental, socio-economic and disadvantages Indicators

From 13:50 to 13:55 the participants (35) were divided into 4 groups:

- **Environmental:** 10 persons (approx. 30 indicators; 3:1) – Moderators: *Joana*
- **Social-Economic:** 10 persons (approx. 30 indicators; 3:1) - Moderators: *Josep*
- **Social-Economic:** 10 persons (approx. 30 indicators; 3:1) - Moderators: *Max*
- **Disadvantages:** 5 persons (approx. 15 indicators; 3:1) – Moderator: *Quim*

From 13:55 to 14:30, each group assessed the assigned indicators concerning their usefulness/relevance and their difficulty to be monitored.

Each participant took 3 tokens (indicators) and assigned their level of **usefulness and difficulty** (see table in Figure 1). Participants could also exclude the indicator(s) in case: were out of scope, link with co-benefit/disadvantage is not clear or difficult to understand/insufficient info. During the process they could consult the supportive table or use internet to search for additional information.

Participants together reviewed the results of each quadrant of the matrix. **To do so, first all tokens (indicators) were turned around and checked if at least 1 indicator for each co-benefit/disadvantage was present in the quadrant “most likely to be selected”** (check the table in Figure 1). Next participants could decide to select indicators from other quadrants (short-term and long-term application, less likely to be selected) or even to recover excluded indicators. Ultimately, at least 1-2 indicators should have been selected per co-benefit/disadvantage.

Figure 1. Group discussion (left) which led to the positioning of the various indicators in the different matrices (right)

Table 1.1 Resume of all co-benefits and disadvantages divided by category.

ENVIRONMENTAL CO-BENEFITS	SOCIO-ECONOMIC	DISADVANTAGES
REDUCTION OF ENERGY DEMAND	FACILITATE ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION	UNDESIRED SPECIES (FAUNE & FLORA)
PROVIDE THERMAL REGULATION	CONTRIBUTION TO LOCAL EMPLOYEMENT	ALLERGIES
IMPROVE / MAINTAIN AIR QUALITY	INCREMENT OF LAND AND PROPERTY MONETARY VALUE	INCREASED FINANCIAL BURDEN
ENHANCE ACOUSTIC CONFORT	INCREASE OF HEALTH AND WELL-BEING	ODOR ISSUES
ENHANCE / PRESERVE BIODIVERSITY	FACILITATE SOCIAL COHESION	HERITAGE VALUES AND CONSERVATION THREATS
PROVIDE CARBON STORAGE / SECUESTRATION	EFFECTS ON AESTHETIC VALUE	SAFETY THREATS
FACILITATE POLLINATION	INCREASE RECREATIONAL VALUE	
INCREMENT OF GREEN AREAS	MAINTAINING / CULTIVATING CULTURAL AND HISTORIC HERITAGE	
GROUNDWATER RECHARGE	INCREASE STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT	
CONTRIBUTE TO FLOOD MITIGATION	REDUCED COSTS	

Finally, 37 indicators were selected, divided in:

- 12 Environmental
- 17 Socio-economic
- 8 Disadvantages

Of all the proposed indicators, 19 were discarded for one of the following options: out of scope, link with co-benefits/disadvantages wasn't clear or because it was difficult to understand/insufficient information.

3.0 Part 2 – Indicators Factsheet

From 14:30 to 15:20 participants kept working on the same groups as before but arranged in pairs. The indicators previously selected were distributed equally among the pairs. Each pair completed the factsheet for their indicators, one factsheet per each combination co-benefit/indicator (see Figure 2). Once the first version of factsheets was finished, they were passed to a different pair for revision of the content (“peer review”). During the process participants could consult the supportive table or use the internet to search for additional information.

Figure 2. Factsheet filled by the experts during the workshop

Finally, 40 different factsheets were created and reviewed, that will help monitoring the co-benefits and disadvantages in the 7 different pilots part of the MULTISOURCE project.

4.0 Part 3 – Next Steps

Responsible	Task	Status	Proposed Deadline
ICRA	<u>Send recommendations for preparing the workshops with stakeholders including suggestion for selecting a representative group of stakeholders for the session and as well “tips” for preparing and carrying out the session. (collaboration with Ana Kalin and ICLEI)</u>	DONE	May 2023
PILOTS	Define who is going to moderate the workshops and send moderators information to ICRA. Name, Institution, email, ENT + water treated, Country.	ONGOING	June 2023
ICRA	Create credential for each moderator in the online interface and send to them.	EXPECTED	June 2023
ICRA	Create a mentimeter file for each pilot. Moderator will be given the mentimeter credentials	EXPECTED	June 2023
PILOTS	Moderators will translate the mentimeter to their native language	EXPECTED	July 2023
PILOTS	Moderators will perform the workshops with their stakeholder	EXPECTED	August to September 2023
ICRA	Prepare factsheets for the selected indicators in the Annual meeting workshop and update the online matrix (to be used during the pilots workshop with stakeholders). Factsheets will be sent to moderators of the workshops as a supportive material.	EXPECTED	June 2023

The overall goal of MULTISOURCE is to, together with local, national, and international stakeholders, demonstrate a variety of about Enhanced Natural Treatment Solutions (ENTS) treating a wide range of urban waters and to develop innovative tools, methods, and business models that support citywide planning and long-term operations and maintenance of nature-based solutions for water treatment, storage, and reuse in urban areas worldwide. The project includes seven pilots treating a wide range of urban waters. Two individual municipalities (Girona, Spain; Oslo, Norway), two metropolitan municipalities (Lyon, France; Milan, Italy), and international partners in Brazil, Vietnam, and the USA will contribute to each of the main project activities: ENTS pilots, risk assessment, business models, technology selection, and the MULTISOURCE Planning Platform. The use of urban archetypes in the Planning Platform will enable users to quickly classify regions (in both developed or developing countries) suitable for the application of nature-based solutions for water treatment (NBSWT) and compare scenarios both with and without NBSWT.

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enhanced natural treatment solutions